

PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS’ COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tili darslarida o‘quvchilarning kommunikativ ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Interaktiv metodlar orqali o‘quvchilarning nutqiy faolligi, muloqot madaniyati, o‘zaro hurmat, hamkorlik va faol ishtirok ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirishning amaliy jihatlari yoritiladi.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются педагогические особенности развития коммуникативных навыков учащихся на уроках английского языка. Особое внимание уделяется интерактивным методам, которые способствуют развитию речи, повышению активности, формированию культуры общения, сотрудничества и взаимного уважения в учебном процессе.

Abstract. This article explores pedagogical methods that help improve students’ communicative skills during English language lessons. The research focuses on real classroom strategies such as role-play activities, pair work and discussion activities. In this article, how interactive teaching methods develop students’ confidence, participation and ability to express opinions in English as well as fostering respectful interaction and communication culture.

Kalit so‘zlar: Ingliz tilini o‘qitish, og‘zaki nutq ko‘nikmalari, kommunikativ kompetensiya, o‘quv jarayoni, o‘quvchi ishtiroki, kommunikativ faoliyatlar, interaktiv ta’lim, sinfdagi o‘zaro muloqot.

Ключевые слова: Обучение английскому языку, навыки устной речи, коммуникативная компетенция, учебный процесс, участие учащихся, коммуникативные виды деятельности, интерактивное обучение, взаимодействие в классе.

Keywords: English language teaching, speaking skills, communicative competence, learning process, student participation, communicative activities, interactive teaching, classroom interaction.

1.INTRODUCTION. In recent decades, developing communicative competence has become important goal in foreign language education. In every aspect of our lives, English is widely used such as in science, education, international communication and professional activities. Therefore, learners are expected not only to understand grammar but also to communicate effectively in real situations. At the same time, English classes also contribute to students’ personal development. During communication activities students work together, listen to each other and respond to different ideas. For this reason, they develop communication culture and social responsibility. The main goal of this article is to examine how specific classroom practices can support the development of students’ communicative skills and show how these practices also contribute to students’ social interaction in learning process.

2.ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC. The idea of communicative competence has been discussed by many researchers in language learning. According to **Brown**, communicative competence is the ability to use language appropriately depending on the situation, not only knowing grammar rules.

Richard and Rodgers explain that communicative language teaching is based on interaction between students. They also argue that language should be learned during communication, where students express ideas, ask questions, and respond to each other. This method changes the focus from teacher-centered instruction to student-centered approach.

Harmer also suggests that learners may learn more effectively when they are engaged in speaking activities. He explains the importance of pair work and group work. By integrating such activities teacher can create more opportunity for learners to practice language in a supportive environment. In this context, interaction becomes a key factor in language development.

Larsen-Freeman and Anderson note that language teaching is a dynamic process process where form, meaning and use are interconnected. They suggest that students understand grammar more effectively when it is presented through meaningful communication rather than isolated exercises.

Ellis approaches language learning from the perspective of acquisition. He explains that interaction creates opportunities for learners to identify gaps in their knowledge and gradually improve their language through use, especially in communicative activities.

Nation focuses on vocabulary development. He explains that students remember new words better when they use them repeatedly in speaking activities, rather than learning them through lists without context.

In context of Uzbek language education, Jalolov also points out that learners achieve better results when lessons include regular speaking tasks rather than only grammar exercises. He emphasizes that students should be given chances to express their ideas during classes. Similarly, Hoshimov and Yakubov suggest that interactive teaching methods, such as pair work and group discussions help students become more confident and fluent during learning process.

These studies show that communicative competence improves most successfully when learners are given opportunities to use language in real situations. Therefore, classroom activities should create conditions where learners can easily interact, express ideas, and respond to others in meaningful ways.

3.MATERIALS AND METHODS. The observations described in this study were conducted during regular English lessons in secondary school lessons. The focus was on how students reacted to different types of speaking tasks.

Several techniques were used during lessons. One of the most effective was role-play, Students did simple activities such as asking for directions or ordering food. At first, many students relied on short phrases, but after a few attempts, they began to make longer responses.

Pair discussions also used in every lesson. For example, students were asked to talk about their daily routines or favorite activities. In pairs, even quieter students started to speak because the situation felt less stressful than speaking in front of the whole class.

Group activities were also implemented. In one activity, learners worked in small groups to decide how to solve a simple problem. During these activities, it was clear that students tried to explain their ideas using basic English, even if their sentences were not always grammatically correct.

During the observation, the attention was given to how often students tried to speak, how actively they participated in pair and group tasks, and how they responded to their classmates during communication activities.

4.RESULTS. At the beginning of the observed lessons, only a small number of people were actively participating. Most students stayed silent, especially when they were unsure about their answers.

After several lessons that includes interactive activities, the situation changed noticeably. More students started answering questions, and pair discussions became more active. Some students who had avoided speaking began to ask simple questions and respond to their classmates.

Role-play activities showed strong results. When students were given clear roles, they focused more on completing the task than on worrying about mistakes. This helped them speak more freely.

Another important observation was related to classroom interaction. Learners began to listen to each other more carefully, waited for their turn to speak, and reacted to their classmates' ideas. This showed not only improvement in language use but also development of communication behavior.

5.DISCUSSION . The observations suggest that students become more active when they are in real situations that require communication rather than passive listening. Pair and group work reduce pressure and allow students to experiment with language.

It was so clear that students did not perfect grammar to speak. Even with limited vocabulary, they could express basic ideas when the task required interaction.

In addition, communicative tasks created a more supportive classroom environment. Students were less afraid of making mistakes because everyone was involved in the same activity. Over time, this helped build confidence.

These activities also help improve simple but important social skills. Students learned to listen, respond, and cooperate during activities. This shows that language lessons can support not only communication skills but also positive interaction between students

6.CONCLUSION. The development of communicative skills requires more than traditional grammar-based teaching. Students need regular chances to speak, interact and use language in real situations.

The classroom observations described in this study show that activities such as role-play, group task and pair discussions can increase students’ participation and confidence. At the same time, these activities support the development of communication culture, including cooperation, respect, and the ability to interact with others. For this reason, English lessons should include more opportunities for active communication and student interaction.

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